

Level of physical activity among undergraduate physiotherapy students of Delhi NCR

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ABSTRACT

Background: Physical inactivity is a major health issue that affects people worldwide and has significant healthcare and economic implications. A significant correlation exists between physical inactivity and the emergence of non-communicable diseases. The present data to date suggest an epidemic of physical inactivity and NCDs in India. PA and physiotherapy practice are closely linked. Physiotherapists perform diverse functions in the healthcare system, requiring them to engage in activities that demand strength, endurance and flexibility. Aims: Thus, the present study aimed to evaluate the physical activity levels of the undergraduate physiotherapy students of Delhi NCR. **Methods and Material:** An observational study was conducted. Young physiotherapy undergraduate students aged 19-24 with normal BMI values of 18-24.9 Kg/m² were included in the study. Data was collected in three parts: demographic data, which obtained the characteristics of the participants; physical activity levels using an International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ) version; and information related to barriers to PA. Descriptive statistics and chi-square test were used for statistical analysis. **Results:** The mean age of participants was 21.08 ± 1.3 years (range 19–24 years), and 62% were males and 38% were females. According to the IPAQ categorical score, a significant percentage of participants were 'inactive' (63%), while only 16% were in the 'Highly active' group. Although many students achieved the MET-minutes threshold for 'Moderate activity' (21%), it was not achieved on at least 5 days of the week, resulting in the majority being classified as 'inactive'. **Conclusions:** A significant negative attitude towards physical activity was observed in a cohort of young- adults with good knowledge about its benefits. The physical fitness level of physiotherapy students is not satisfactory compared to the profession's physical demands.

Key-words: Physiotherapy, Physical Fitness, Non-Communicable Diseases

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Introduction

Physical inactivity is a major health issue that affects people worldwide and has significant healthcare and economic implications¹. There is a significant correlation between physical inactivity and the emergence of non-communicable diseases (NCDs), as evidenced by various literature^{2,3}. This correlation negatively affects the mental health, and quality of life of the individual and leads to premature deaths^{4,5}. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), more than 80% of deaths caused by NCDs occur in low-middle-income countries⁶. The present data to date suggest an epidemic of physical inactivity and NCDs in India^{7,8,9}. India contributes almost 2/3rd of the mortality rate due to the NCDs^{8,10}. According to the literature, physical activity (PA) has been proven to help prevent different NCDs to decrease the global burden and suggests that focusing on PA is the way ahead¹¹. WHO suggests that creating active environments must achieve a 15% reduction in physical inactivity by 2025.^{12,13} This reduction

leads to curbing the development of NCDs^{12,13}. In a country as diverse as India, tackling this issue requires a multi-pronged approach. Increasing PA in a society can be achieved through three segments; firstly to promote PA at the national level aided by national guidelines and developing national PA programs and promoting PA at the population level to bridge gaps⁷. Secondly, understanding the environment is crucial in improving PA, as is incorporating PA benefits into education and curriculum¹³. Furthermore, by indulging the PA benefits in our education system and curriculum, we imbibe PA in society's social and cultural norms⁹. Literature suggests that strategies like incorporating practical sessions and behaviour change activities in the health professional education system can reduce the risk of NCDs⁹. Addressing barriers, beliefs, and myths related to PA and NCDs is also important, with community-level efforts needed to change beliefs and myths^{14,15}, while barriers differ among age groups. Adolescents associate physical inactivity with electronic gadgets and lethargy, while in the middle age group, it is associated with a lack of time, motivation and interest^{14,15}.

PA and physiotherapy practice are closely linked¹⁶. Studies also suggest that for decades physiotherapists have been using PA and exercise to manage NCDs and other conditions^{16,17,18,19}. Physiotherapists perform diverse functions in the healthcare system, requiring them to engage in activities that demand strength, endurance and flexibility²⁰. Physiotherapy students need to reach a reasonably high level of physical fitness to carry out their routine job activities²⁰. However, the curriculum and academic experience do not currently pay attention to the physical fitness levels of physiotherapy students²⁰. Therefore, this study addresses undergraduate physiotherapy students which represents a larger group of young adults expected to have a good working knowledge of physical activity and related health benefits. Furthermore, graduate physiotherapists may be considered important health advocates. They are expected to promote and prescribe exercise to patients and the general public. It is important to identify if there are any gaps between the knowledge and personal practice of physiotherapy students, particularly concerning their motives and barriers to engagement in physical activity²¹.

Thus, the present study aimed to evaluate the physical activity levels of the undergraduate-level physiotherapy students of Delhi NCR.

Subjects and Methods

An observational study was conducted following ethical approval by the institutional ethical committee. All male and female young physiotherapy undergraduate students were included in the study, aged between 19-24 years, with normal BMI values of 18-24.9 Kg/m². If the students were diagnosed or had any history of neurological and musculoskeletal or any other disorder, they were excluded from the study. A total of 100 undergraduate-level participants participated in the study from Delhi NCR and gave their consent to participate. All the procedure was explained to the participants before taking part in this study.

Data was collected in 3 parts; first demographic data which obtains the characteristics of the participants, second part obtains physical activity levels using an International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ) long version and the last part takes the information related to barriers of PA.

IPAQ has two versions, short form (9 items) and long-form (31 items). Both versions are used to assess the PA during the last 7 days and the questionnaire can be filled by telephonic interview or self-reported. IPAQ has shown an acceptable validity when measuring PA in the Indian population and reliability (ICC>90)²².

Procedure

All 100 physiotherapy students were included in the study and IPAQ long form was administered to assess the physical activity levels and energy expenditure as shown in Figure 1. This questionnaire has 31 items that estimate physical activity levels and are categorised into 4 domains: at work, transportation, housework and leisure during the last 7 days. Physical activity in the present study is expressed as categorical and continuous measurements as defined by the IPAQ. The continuous score estimates the weekly energy expenditure expressed in MET minutes/week (Metabolic Equivalent-Minutes) obtained by multiplying the value of energy expenditure for the given physical activity in METs by the weekly frequency (days per week) and the time in minutes (minutes per day).

The categorical score classifies an individual into one of three categories: 'Inactive', 'Moderately active' and, 'Highly active'.

Figure 1: Procedure of the study

Statistical Analysis: Data was managed on an Excel sheet and SPSS 21.0 version. Descriptive statistics and chi-square test were used for analysis.

Results

Out of 357 participants, 100 participants were included in the study based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. The mean age of participants was 21.08 ± 1.3 years (range 19–24 years), and 62% were males and 38% were females as shown in **Table 1**.

Table- 1: Descriptive data of participants

Characteristics	Mean ± SD	Range	No.	%
Male	--	--	62	62.0
Female	--	--	38	38.0
Age	21.08 ± 1.3	19-24	--	--
1 st Year	20.05 ± 0.7	19-21	--	--
2 nd Year	20.05 ± 0.9	19-21	--	--
3 rd Year	20.08 ± 1.1	19-22	--	--
4 th Year	22.0± 1.38	22-24	--	--
Height 'cm'	164.11 ± 9.92	154.6 -175.3	--	--
Weight 'kg'	58.1235 ± 9.82	48.6 - 69.0	--	--

The mean values of weekly total MET minutes of the study population were 1678.50 ±1730.92 (males 1208.90 ± 1090.09 and females 2420.85 ± 2272.85) as shown in **Table 2**.

According to the IPAQ categorical score, a significant percentage of participants were 'inactive' (63%), while only 16% were in the 'Highly active' group. Although many students achieved the MET-minutes threshold for 'Moderate activity' (21.0%), it was not achieved on at least 5 days of the week, resulting in the majority being classified as 'inactive' (**Table-2**).

Table-2: MET values

MET Values	Mean + SD	Range	No.	%
Mean MET Values	1678.50 ±1730.92	1208.90-2420.85	--	--
Mean MET Values (M)	1208.90 ± 1090.09	1208.90-1090.09	62	62.0
Mean MET Values (F)	2420.85 ± 2272.85	2420.85-2272.85	38	38.0
Inactive	--	--	63	63.0
Moderately Active	--	--	21	21.0
Highly Active	--	--	16	16.0

In the specific domains, physical inactivity was higher during 'leisure time' than in other domains, with most being relatively active in the transport and household chores domains. Females were more active than males in other domains except the leisure-time activity domain as shown in **Table -3**.

Table - 3: Percentage of Barriers to Engaging in Physical Activity (For Inactive (N=63))

Barriers	No.	%	Male		Female	
			No.	%	No.	%
Time	38	60.32	19	30.15	6	9.52
Motivation And Support	10	15.87	8	12.69	2	3.17
Facilities	5	7.937	11	17.46	5	7.93
Personal	10	15.87	9	14.28	3	4.76

Discussion

The current study aimed to evaluate the physical activity levels of undergraduate-level physiotherapy students. A total of 100 students, with greater heterogeneity in gender with 62% of the male sample size. The students of Delhi NCR had a similar undergraduate-level profile in occupation. Our results show that 63% of students were inactive as indicated by IPAQ-long and it is suggested that students were not sufficiently involved in physical activity necessary for reducing health risk factors. Only 21% of students were involved in moderate PA and 16% were engaged in high PA. Our findings also support the previous studies which were conducted globally.

A recent systematic review highlighted that the majority of South Asians are physically inactive, especially during leisure time²³. Our results support these findings, however, it is particularly alarming as the current cohort could be considered unique and expected to be active, as they are constantly exposed to the importance of PA in their academic curriculum. Furthermore, patients adopt physical exercise regimes as the participants are trained in the prescription, education and motivation of their patients. Hence, our results indicate a negative correlation between the knowledge and practice in this group of young adults. Similar studies conducted in developed countries like Australia and Latvia among physiotherapy students and physiotherapists have indicated that the majority of the participants were either 'Moderately' or 'Highly' active^{24,25}. Several studies have shown that healthcare workers exhibit the same unhealthy behaviours as the general population. Similarly, evidence also demonstrates that the personal health behaviours and attitudes of health professionals may influence how they practice clinically and may also influence how patients view their credibility as health promoters²⁶. By using qualitative methods one can explore the reasons for the observed discrepancy between knowledge and practice in these groups.

Our results demonstrate that insufficient time, lack of motivation and support, inadequate facilities and other personal reasons were the primary contributing factors towards physical inactivity in this group. Perceived lack of time is a well-known barrier to engagement in physical activity, especially among young adults due to occupational and educational commitments²⁷. Sallis et al. found that, after control for individual characteristics, closer proximity and higher density of exercise facilities were

significantly associated with increased frequency of exercise⁴⁸. Statistically significant positive changes in the overall fitness measures within the intervention community were noticed after reducing barriers to PA including increasing the availability of physical activity-related equipment and facilities²⁸. However, all these 'external' barriers can be overcome with the correct attitude and motivation. The most important finding from the present study is the significant negative attitude towards physical activity expressed by study participants. This attitude appears to stem from earlier in life due to a lack of support and motivation for physical exercise and sports, received during primary and secondary schooling. Many expressed they were more focused on academic work during childhood and adolescence acting on guidance received from their parents and teachers. As is the case elsewhere, it is difficult to have a career based solely on sport. Self-efficacy is defined as one's belief in their capabilities to accomplish a specific task. There appears to be a greater opportunity to mediate behaviour through cognitive control than when behaviour has become more habitual²⁹.

The role played by self-efficacy in physical activity behaviour appears to be quite consistent across ages and populations³⁰. Higher levels of self-efficacy are known to be associated with participation in more physical activity³¹. Those with high self-efficacy for walking, stronger intentions to be active, and an activity plan were twice as likely to meet the physical activity recommendations³². The perceived low efficacy in the present cohort can become a significant barrier to the initiation and maintenance of PA. Incorporation theory of self-efficacy into the design of exercise intervention is beneficial and is an important factor that needs to be considered when planning PA interventions. These negative attitudes have become a significant 'internal' barrier, which has not been changed despite the education received about the importance of physical activity. This negative attitude also persists despite evidence suggesting a positive relationship between physical activity/exercise/ sports and academic performance³³. Better outcomes are likely by changing the attitudes and beliefs of parents and teachers through carefully planned educational programmes and other interventions.

Furthermore, university policies should change to encourage exercise and sports among undergraduates and provide facilities close to university premises. It is evident from our findings that psychosocial constructs need to be given careful consideration when planning interventions to promote physical activity. The socio-ecological approach emphasizes that health promotion should focus not only on intrapersonal behavioural factors but also on the multiple-level factors that influence the specific behaviour in question³⁴. The socio-ecological model helps us to identify opportunities to promote physical activity by recognising the individual (e.g. sex, beliefs and attitudes), behavioural (passive and active time), social environmental (family, teachers, peers) and physical environmental (e.g. availability of equipment and facilities) factors that may influence one's ability to be sufficiently physically active³⁵.

The results from the present study recognize such individual level and physical environmental factors that influence physical activity. Hence there is a need for using comprehensive interventional models addressing multiple factors when planning health promotional activities in the present population. This study helped to fill a recognized research gap in the region and identified a key primary 'internal' barrier to physical activity among young adults. The qualitative methods used were rigorous and the study suggested some new findings regarding perceptions of physical activity. There are several limitations in the present study³⁶. Furthermore, physical activity in the present study was self-reported using the IPAQ questionnaire which typically overestimates physical activity^{37,38}. Despite this, self-report remains the simplest, most feasible and affordable instrument for physical activity surveillance. This study has several limitations like less number of sample size, randomisation not being performed due to this recruitment method being biased, and causality not being established using this methodology.

Conclusion

In this group of young adults, the observed physical activity level was low, with a majority being physically inactive. A significant negative attitude towards physical activity was observed in a cohort of young- adults with good knowledge about its benefits. The physical fitness level of physiotherapy students is not satisfactory compared to the profession's physical demands. There is a need to improve the fitness of physiotherapy students by making changes in curriculum and teaching methodologies. To implement things effectively, it may be recommended that the physical fitness of students carry some weight in the evaluation process during studies.

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